

TRANSFORMING RURAL AREAS THROUGH RURBANIZATION: A CASE STUDY OF TELANGANA STATE

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Abstract

As per Census of India statistics, the rural population in India, stands at 833 million, constituting almost 68% of the total population. Telangana is the newly formed state of India. It has a vast rural population which has a lot of scope in the development of rural areas. Rurbanisation is new concept which has more importance in developing the rural areas with the assimilation of urban facilities. Rurbanisation can cater the needs of rural people with better facilities and infrastructure. It has its advantages empowering the rural people with the facilities like electrification which has the major utility in Agricultural sector of rural areas. Rurbanization aims to create a cluster of villages and provide urban amenities to the people living within that cluster. Thus, the aim is to create a big village with an urban feel. This will help in improving the quality of life of people in the rural areas and help to reduce the urban-rural divide which will ultimately reduce the rural to urban migration.

Rurbanization process is the rural areas transform into urban areas. It is highly affected by the geographical, political, environmental, and economic constraints and opportunities. Effective implementation of government schemes facilitates the process of rural transformation.

It also has some drawbacks as lack of political will, Delay in funds disbursement and geographical factors like topography makes it difficult for the implementation of Rurbanisation, mostly in North –East areas.

Keywords: Agricultural sector, Amenities, Migration, Electrification, Rurbanization, Urbanization, Development, Geographical factors, Topography, Rural, Cluster, Hilly, Tribal, Desert area, Public Private Partnership (PPP) model.

1.Introduction

The world is transforming rapidly. Hereto isolated rural areas are getting connected through the networks of communication. The process of linking initiated by colonization has gained momentum in the second half of the twentieth century. End of colonial era left the world closely linked than ever before.

Newly liberated nations busied themselves in reconstruction and reformation of their impoverished rural agrarian societies. Rurbanization is a process of rural transformation. It is not yet caught attention urban planners but it is a prominent development process commonly witnessed in developing countries. Predominantly rural agriculture economy, forms of settlements, lifestyles, and social attitudes are changing and new rurban form is emerging. This paper describes some of the salient features of the process of rurbanization, indicates its origin, and discusses some of the effects the process has brought about. By borrowing metaphor from biology, one can describe suburban sprawl as process of grafting urban lifestyle on rural space. Rurbanization is a process of altering rural forms with pre-selected urban patterns and lifestyles.

Rurbanisation denotes to the rural area being urbanized, precisely rural area with the characteristic features of facilities available in area. These include Education (School), Health (PHC), Pucca road to the village, Electrification of the village and establishing new markets. The Rurbanisation possess various characteristic features which has a lot of scope in development of the rural area. These are the major facilities includes Rurbanization

1. Mobile health units
2. Provision of drinking water
3. Electrification
4. LPG connections
5. E-governance initiatives that will involve internet connectivity for provision for basic civic services and more.
- 6.Skill development training along with economic activities
- 7.Digital literacy
- 8.Provision of fully equipped mobile health unit

9. Inter-village road connectivity
10. Citizen service centres
11. E-gram connectivity
12. Public transport facilities
13. LPG gas connections
14. Agro processing
15. Agro services including storage and warehousing
16. Sanitation facilities
17. Provision of piped water supply
18. Solid and liquid waste management
19. Upgrading education facilities

2. Objective

The objectives of the Rurbanization is to stimulate local economic development, and to create well planned Rurban cluster.

This can be achieved in the three ways:

- To improve social and infrastructural development in the rural areas.
- Improving the life of people of the rural clusters bridging the rural urban divide.
- Reducing distress migration from rural to urban areas.
- Basic delivery of facilities to village dwellers.
- Promote integrated development of rural areas with provision of quality housing, better connectivity, employment opportunities and supporting physical and social infrastructure.
- Reduce migration from rural to urban areas due to lack of basic services and sufficient economic activities in rural areas.
- Internal roads within village settlement, Efficient Mass Transportation systems to improve connectivity between urban and rural areas, public transportation facilities that need to be

developed like bus stops, transport depot etc.

□ Identification of sanitation facilities that need improvement – sewerage and drainage line for household connection, door to door solid waste collection & dumping facilities.

The objective is to create a big village with an urban feel. This will help in improving the quality of life of people in the rural areas and rural divide which will ultimately reduce the rural to urban migration.

These include,

- It will create a development central hub for a cluster of villages
- Connect all the nearby villages and provide economical support to
- It will lead to decentralization of activities from rural (through Rurban centres)
- Enhance financial inclusion, infrastructure, social benefits to masses
- Create more accessible markets for farmers' yield
- Encourages participation of private sector by support of government (with critical gap funding)
- Backward states and north eastern states will gain a lot from this.

3. Origin of Problem

The concept of Rurbanization is newly emerging in recent decades throughout in world, but India has been taking baby steps to meet its target of to development the rural areas transformation into the urban areas though Shyam Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission scheme. The research intends to focus on advantages and disadvantages of Rurbanization.

4. Methodology

In Telangana Rural people lives in 62% while urban people live in 38%. These 62% of people major occupation is agriculture. These people lives are associated rural areas. In this study majorly focuses and understanding of the concept of rurbanization and their impact of rurbanization.

Study the selected clusters of rurbanization in different districts in Telangana state.

The study focuses this area's collected from various books, international journals, government reports, publication from various websites focuses on the Rurbanization.

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5. Study area

Figure.1. Geography of Study area.

6. Rurbanization of Telangana

The government of Telangana has proposed 18 rurban clusters to the Indian government. The rurban clusters villages with a population of 25000-50000 in plain areas and 5000-15000 in tribal, hilly and desert areas. The funding of the project will be through various schemes of the Government. The project will be implemented through the Public Private Partnership (PPP) model.

Telangana state proposed eighteen cluster to central government. The central government approved the total eighteen clusters.

The proposed clusters in Telangana are,

Table: Rurban clusters in Telangana State.

S.NO.	CLUSTER NAME	SUB DISTRICT	DISTRICT
1	Allapur	Tandur	Rangareddy
2	Ryakal	Narayanakhed	Medak
3	Jukkal	Jukkal	Kamareddy
4	Chirragunta	Mandamarri	Manchiryala
5	Sarangapalle	Mandamarri	Manchiryala
6	Vennacharla	Peddakothapally	Nagarkarnool
7	Narlapur	Tadvai	Bhupalapally
8	Kuntala	Kuntala	Nirmal
9	Kondabhimanapalle	Devarakonda	Nalgonda
10	Choutuppall	Choutuppall	Yadadri bhuvanagiri
11	Yedapalle	Yedapalle	Nizamabad
12	Bijirisharif	Jammikunta	Karimnagar
13	Papannapeta	Papannapeta	Medak
14	Shankarpalle	Shankarpalle	Rangareddy
15	Jaligon	Gajwel	Siddipet
16	Nanacharla	Gandeed	Mahabubnagar
17	Sulthanabad	Sulthanabad	Peddapally
18	Nagaram	Bhupalapally	Bhupalapally

Source: Shyam Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission Scheme, India

Geographic Distribution Summary:

The list covers a wide range of districts, showing a diverse spread across the state. Notably:

- **Manchiryala, Medak, Rangareddy, and Bhupalapally** appear multiple times, suggesting these areas have several active clusters mentioned in your records.
- The clusters range from Northern districts like **Nirmal** to Southern regions like **Nagarkarnool**.

Table 2. Count of clusters with districts

Count	Name of the District
2	Rangareddy
2	Medak
2	Manchiryala
2	Bhupalapally
1	Kamareddy
1	Nagarkarnool
1	Nirmal
1	Nalgonda
1	Yadadri bhuvanagiri
1	Nizamabad
1	Karimnagar
1	Siddipet
1	Mahabubnagar
1	Peddapally

Source: Shyam Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission Scheme, India

Figure 2. Count Of Clusters with Districts

7. Characteristics of Rurbanization

Rurbanisation is the construction and maintenance of infrastructure and ‘urban’ buildings within rural kebele boundaries, a process which accelerated everywhere. The infrastructures and buildings involved are:

1. Internal roads and paths

2. Electricity infrastructure
3. Mobile phone infrastructure
4. Water infrastructure: reservoirs; irrigation structures; protected springs, boreholes, wells
5. Health service buildings
6. Schools
7. Urban settlements of residential and non-farm business buildings.
8. Approach road.
9. A pucca road starting from the village entrance up to the village Chora.
10. Providing drinking water facilities.
11. Construction and renovations of village ponds with bathing ghats.
12. Construction of primary schoolrooms / balwadis / Anganwadi's.
13. Community Halls.
14. Development of village pasture.
15. Construction of panchayat ghats.
16. Electrification
17. Soak-wells / soak –pits
18. Individual / community latrines.
19. Shifting of ukardas at the entrance of the village to an alternate site.
20. Tree plantation along the main road of the village.
21. Afforestation in the Gaucher / wasteland.

In each community differences in the difficulty of the terrain, settlement patterns, and the physical locations of these infrastructures and buildings generated differential access to safe water, irrigation, electricity, mobile phone use, modern health and education services, and urban personal services.

8. Advantages of Rurbanization

1. It will reduce the rural-urban divide by providing physical and communication connectivity.
2. Reverse migration will be promoted due to the availability of urban amenities and jobs.
3. Purchasing power of rural inhabitants will increase due to employment opportunities.
4. It will help utilize India's demographic dividend since rural inhabitants will have access to skill development centres.
5. The Smart Cities Mission will receive a boost as the revamped smart cities will not have to bear the burden of rural migration.

Disadvantages of Rurbanization

1. It will require coordination between numerous entities-Union Rural development Ministry, State governments and private sector to succeed.
2. The Rurban clusters will be developed through the Private Public Partnership (PPP) model. However, this will lead to an increase in operating costs.
3. Private companies might not be willing to partner the government in developing rurban clusters in areas with law-and-order issues like J& K and the North East.

Challenges

- Already there are several schemes for rural development and this may create overlap and delicacy, so better integration needed.
- Greater involvement of Panchayat Raj Institutions (PRI) needed with bottom-up area-specific approach required else it won't generate much development.
- Digital literacy and e-governance will be difficult in the absence of Information Technology Communication (ITC) infrastructure.
- Close coordination between centre, state and district needed to make it successful.

With effective implementation this is a step in right direction.

9. Conclusion

Rurbanization is an emerging and potentially most important transformative process, observed in few pockets of the large third world, developing countries. It is fundamentally a process of transformation of rural areas by introduction of certain urban characteristics. It brings about differential growth patterns.

However, it is not based on the domination paradigm (domination of man over nature or state over citizens) and is fundamentally not an exploitative process. It is more of a regenerative, restorative and revitalizing process. Its emphasis is on healing the wounds suffered during the colonial rule. It positively affects people and environment. Its emphasis is on judicious consumption of resources. It combines traditional knowledge and practices with modern technology. It is a distributive and participatory process, which brings about changes in the lifestyles of participants. Modern technologies such as telecommunication and information technology can further and strengthen the process. It has potential of combining local actions with a global vision. Future oriented rurbanization can make the world a better place to live.

The development of rural areas in each and every state of India is the need of the hour. With increasing the rural to urban migration, urban cities are mostly affected due to the scarcity of resources. To mitigate the rural to urban migration and proper use of available resources in the rural areas Rurbanisation plays a key role. States like Telangana which are at early stages of development Rurbanisation serves the purpose of development in most of the rural clusters.

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